

DEVELOPMENT OF STRUCTURAL SYSTEM IN WORLD LINGUISTICS.

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Annotation

Analysis of the research of verbs of action in European and Uzbek linguistics, defining a specific direction of the research on this basis; determining the amount and limit of action verbs, that is, defining the semantic field of these verbs; implementation of semantic classification of verb-lexemes: identification of their common, differentiating symbols.

Key words

semantic syntagma, lexeme, word meaning, semantic field, logical fragments, paradigmatic and syntagmatic, semes.

As noted by the first President I.A.Karimov: "Adjusting our way of thinking to the spirit of independence, giving up one-sided and narrow thinking is one of the most important issues of today's period of Spiritual revival" [1 Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development. Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1997, pp. 150-151]1. This deep thought is directly related to linguistics, and a number of researches and researches being created today originate from these requirements.

Comprehensive research of specific semantic fields is one of the researches in this way. After all, the analysis of certain semantic fields of words has its own philosophical value. Because people rebuild and shape their worldview based on their history, traditions, and life experience.

Due to the fact that the word is the material base and material of every phrase, sentence and text, the process of exchange of ideas takes place from words and their semantic-syntactic connection. At the same time, the determination of the lexical meaning of the word - the speech activation of certain semes, the connection with the semes of other lexemes, the formation of a certain semantic syntagm occurs, so that the study of the function of the word in speech becomes a central issue of linguistics.

Because the study of a word in speech, its ability to be combined with other words, the formation of a semantic syntagm, the fact that it requires certain words

and word forms to fully reveal its meaning is related to the valence theory's substantial-semantic phenomenon of word meaning, the manifestation of word meaning in a sentence [Rasulov R. Status verbs in the Uzbek language and their obligatory valences. T., 1989, 141 p.10-p.].

The combination of words, the logical connection between them is realized primarily according to the meaning possibility (substantial feature) of language units. The socio-practical, scientific value of language as a means of communication comes from the fact that its units have a content aspect, expressing a concept [Rasulov R.O., Narzieva N. Learning lexicology. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1992, p. 17].

So, the semantic connection of words directly reveals the semantic relationship of their meanings. If the combination of a certain word with another word occurs according to its semantic possibility, in this case, the question of the relationship between the required and demanding words arises. The semantic relationship between words creates a direct syntactic relationship, creates syntactic structures. That is, the syntactic relationship is based on the semantic relationship, semantics and syntax are dialectically related, more precisely, valence is the crossing point of grammar and lexis, syntax and semantics [Stepanova M.D. The theory of valence and valence analysis. - M., 1973, p. 69.].

The semantic structure of the word is directly connected with the meaning (semema). As you know, there is no meaning without semantic construction. Each meaning is evaluated according to its structure and content. Forming the content side of a known word, it performs a specific task in language and speech together with its sound basis - expression side (form).

The meaning of the word, the meaning structure consists of certain logical parts, constituent parts (sema). Semas shape the meaning of words, ensuring that each meaning exists as a separate linguistic "unit". The symbols of word meaning carry a certain meaning in speech. Therefore, small logical components of the meaning of the word are in relation to a mutually stable whole (system) and serve as a verbal "expression" of the meaning. Therefore, as mentioned above, studying and analyzing the meaning structure of a word, identifying the logical parts of a word's meaning, determining the types of its components, clarifying the place and significance of each seme in the meaning (sememe), revealing its relation to other semes - finding a logical connection between meanings (semantic formation of a syntagm) - accordingly, it allows to enter the mutual paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of words, to create a series of words, to identify and find the patterns that distinguish words from each other in a paradigmatic relationship. These results are of scientific and practical significance for semasiology, lexicography, lexicology,

computer linguistics, linguistics in general. Accordingly, it is important to study the meaning structure and composition of English and Uzbek verbs, in particular, active verbs.

When determining the conjugation of action verbs, we mainly use the linguistic-semantic theory - its differential-semantic analysis method. Because the method of learning the meaning of a word by dividing it into components, that is, component analysis (hereafter KT)[Hojiev A. Annotated dictionary of linguistic terms. -Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. 2002, p. 51] method is the most basic and convenient method for determining the structure and meaning of words.

It is known that dividing the lexeme seme into components, semes, is called analysis method. This method is recognized as the main method for studying the meaning of language units in systematic linguistics[Nematov H., Rasulov R. Basics of system lexicology of the Uzbek language. T., "Teacher", 1995, p. 66]. Because this method makes it possible to determine, interpret and describe the semantic content of countless terms and words with the help of numbered terms. In this respect, KT essentially reminds the elements of D. I. Mendeleev's periodic table in the material world. Because the essence of semas is similar to chemical elements. Just as one element participates in the composition of different substances in different compounds and creates different substances, one seme participates as an element in the meaning structure of hundreds and even thousands of words. Therefore, the future of this method is bright. It has the same character as the separation of substances into their components in chemistry.

It is known that the CT method was first used in phonology, then in grammar (in the works of R. Jakobson, A. Martine), and then in semantics. In current linguistics, CT is used in the analysis of the meaning of lexical, morphological and syntactic units[Guliga E.V., Shendels E.I. O componentnom analize znachimyx edinits zhyzyka// Principy i metody semanticheskikh issledovaniy. - M., 1976.].

Therefore, through CT, we will have the opportunity to know the internal structure of the language as a system, in particular, the secrets of the structural structure of the language semantic system. The CT method is an integral continuation of the theory of semantic fields. This is discussed separately in the 3rd chapter of the work entitled "Osnovy komponentnogo analiza" [Akhmanova O.S. i dr. Basic component analysis. - M., MGU, 1969. -S.45-64.].

It is known that in the East, cleaning the semantic field of words was completed and started again[Islamov Z.M. Mahmud Zamakhshari's "Muqaddimat ul-adab" written sources and the collective scientific-critical text of the Arabic-

Turkish vocabulary. Ph.D. Diss. autoref. - Tashkent, 1998, p. 45. Proof of this can be seen in the dictionaries of Zamakhshari "Muqaddimat-ul Adab" (1128-1143) and Chingiz's "Kelurnoma" (1659-1707). In these dictionaries, specific semantic fields are provided by language, each semantic field is assigned to the quality of the dictionary [Islamov Z.M. Referenced abstract, p. 46]. But in these dictionaries, the semantic fields are approached only practically. No attention has been paid to working on the theoretical aspects of the word semantic field.

The theoretical study of the word semantic field was mainly founded by the German linguist Y. Trier. In his monograph "Study of German vocabulary in semantic fields" he researched the meaning of words, mainly by linking them to concepts [Trier J. Einleitung // Der deutsche Wortschatz im Sinnbezirk des Verstandes. - Heidelberg. 1931; this author. Sprachliche Felder // Zeitschrift für deutsche Bildung. 1932, Bd.8.Nf.9.-S.417-425.]. That is why Y. Trier groups the field of words based on the field of concepts. According to the scientist, every field of understanding is always covered by words, none of it should be left empty. The words representing each concept field constitute a word semantic field. A word gives meaning only in its field and the opposite outside of it. The development of word meaning is the redistribution of the conceptual space in words. From the point of view of philosophy, the opinions of Y. Trier can be considered correct. Because when mankind gained the concept of objective existence, it created words to express it. The creation of words is undoubtedly related to the concepts of the people who speak this language. So, the development of the concepts of objective existence, in turn, is the word

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